

Synthesis and Structural Studies of Bis(acetoacetanilido)dioxomolybdenum(VI) Complex

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A bis(acetoacetanilido)dioxomolybdenum(VI) complex was prepared and examined by various physical methods in order to test proposed structure-rearrangement criteria. The work provides a scope for determination and aquation of molybdenum(VI) in the presence of acetoacetanilide.

BIDENTATE β -ketoanilides in which the donor atoms are oxygen have been extensively investigated¹⁻³ as solid analytical reagents, since many hard metal ions are known for quantitative formation of complexes with definite stoichiometry. Simplest β -ketoanilide, acetoacetanilide has the possibility of acting as an ambidentate ligand as coordination through nitrogen (1) is possible in addition to the expected linkages through oxygen atoms (2, 3). However, the resonating structures of amide group (4), suggest the donation through oxygen because of its higher electronegativity⁴. The effects of substitution in benzene ring⁵ revealed similar bonding in metal chelates as was also evidenced from mass and ir spectra of copper(II) chelates.

In the present investigation we synthesised yellow and green coloured mononuclear dioxocomplexes of Mo^{VI} with acetoacetanilide (HAA)₂ and studied their chemical structures by ir, ¹H nmr and mass spectra including X-ray studies of powdered compounds. It has been established that the yellow complex, MoO₂(AA)₂, has the *cis* structure with the unsymmetrical⁶ reagent HAA. However, spectral, magnetic, tlc and thermal studies helped to conclude the structure⁶ MoO₂(AA)₂ for both the yellow and green compounds. The quantitative precipitation of MoO₂(AA)₂ by HAA leaves a scope for the determination of Mo^{VI} by HAA.

Experimental

Dioxo complexes of Mo^{VI} with acetoacetanilide: Ammonium molybdate (0.8 g) dissolved in water (10 ml) was warmed on a water-bath, the pH of the solution adjusted to about 2 using dilute HNO₃. To it an ethanolic solution (10 ml) containing acetoacetanilide (1.6 g) was added with stirring when a yellow precipitate was formed. The mixture was digested on a water-bath for 15 min and filtered. The resulting yellow solid was washed several times with water and finally with ethanol and dried at 110°, (20 g). The above yellow compound on digestion with mineral acid (pH < 1) or simply by heating at ~140° produced the green compound. The synthesis could also be done in presence of dilute HCl or H₂SO₄.

Physicochemical measurements: Ir spectra (KBr) of the compounds were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 527 spectrophotometer, mass spectra on a Hewlett-Packard 5995B spectrometer, and ¹H nmr spectra ligand in CDCl₃ and complexes in acetone-d₆ on a Varian EM-390 90 MHz instrument. Data collection and analysis were done on a Hewlett-Packard 59970a workstation. Sample was introduced using a direct insertion probe heated from 30° to 350° at a rate of 45°/min at an internal pressure of 10 to -6 torr. Thermal analysis data were recorded with Al₂O₃ in a photorecording metriplex OD-120 (Hungary) derivatograph. Silver plated powder sample was used for dielectric constant and loss measurement at room temperature (30°) by a HP 1392 impedance analyser.

Results and Discussion

Elemental analysis of the yellow and green coloured diamagnetic dioxo-complexes of Mo^{VI} with acetoacetanilide are listed in Table 1. Thermal decomposition studies of the complexes indicate that the first and final decomposition points are 150° and 200°, respectively. The percentage loss in weight at the final stage, both calculated and

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL DATA OF MoO₂(AA)₂ COMPLEXES

Compound MoO ₂ (AA) ₂	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)				ΔM Ω ⁻¹ cm ² mol ⁻¹
	O	H	N	Mo	
Yellow	47.9 (50.0)	4.0 (4.2)	5.82 (5.85)	19.12 (19.99)	6.0
Green	47.1 (50.9)	4.0 (4.3)	5.3 (5.9)	19.73 (20.34)	7.0

observed, have also been recorded to indicate the purity of the complex. The TG and DTA curves clearly show that both the complexes have the composition of MoO₂(AA)₂. The yellow complex shows green shades when heated to ~140°. This may be due to the change in crystallinity only which was further authenticated by molecular weight determinations by freezing point depression and tlc studies on silica gel with varied solvent systems. Hence, we report the results only for the yellow complex. The solubilities of both the variety are very poor in common organic solvents. But the complex is fairly soluble in acetone. Both the yellow and green compounds produce molybdenum blue in water in the pH range 6.0–7.0 when digested on a water-bath. The green variety is converted to a water-insoluble reddish brown compound of unidentified composition when digested at ~50° in aqueous medium even in N₂ atmosphere.

The X-ray powder diffraction pattern of the yellow complex does not indicate any well-defined pattern of the complex. The most intense line is at 10.78 Å indicating a preferential orientation of this plane corresponding to this interplanar spacing. All other lines are fifteen to thirty times weaker than the previous one.

The dielectric constant and loss measured by impedance analyser over a wide range of frequency (13–40 KHz) of the complex are 8.5 and 0.08, respectively, at room temperature (35°).

Most characteristic bands for the ligand acetoacetanilide in the ir spectra are at 3 280–3 240br (N–H), 1 715 (C=O), 1 660 (amide C=O), 1 600 (NH bend) and 1 540 cm⁻¹ (C=C). The molybdenum complex MoO₂(AA)₂, however, showed many of the bands along with several additional peaks characteristic for Mo–O. The peaks at 3 330 (NH), 1 715 (C=O), 1 630 (amide C=O), 1 555 (C=C) and 935 cm⁻¹ (Mo–O) are also rationalised for the complex. The ligand as well as the complex showed strong bands at 750 and 460 cm⁻¹.

The ¹H nmr spectra of ligand acetoacetanilide is very simple which supports the presence of only one form. The two methylene protons adjacent to two C=O groups appear at δ 3.4 and the acetyl methyl protons appear at δ 2.15, both being very sharp singlets. The broad signal at δ 9.2–8.8 accounts for the proton attached to nitrogen (CO–NH–C₆H₅). All the aromatic protons appear as multiplets in the aromatic region (δ 7.5–6.9). The spectrum of the complex (yellow) is in good agreement with the structure 5. All the peaks

appeared in the spectrum are in conformity with those of the ligand itself. The appearance of a sharp singlet at δ 9.65 accounts for the proton attached to nitrogen. The olefinic proton appears at δ 6.4 as a very sharp singlet, and the acetyl methyl protons are embedded in the peaks which appeared for acetone-d₆ (the solvent used) at δ 2.05. The aromatic protons showed multiplets at δ 7.6–7.0.

Natural molybdenum contains a mixture of isotopes ⁹⁸Mo and ⁹⁶Mo. The isotope pattern for ions containing two Mo atoms can be predicted by well-established methods⁷ from the isotope distribution of metal. The reported relative abundance data are based on the heights of the signals of the ions containing the isotope ⁹⁸Mo⁶. The mass spectrum of the complex 5 did not show the molecular ion peak probably due to the thermal instability, instead, it showed a peak of very low intensity at m/z 318 in the highest mass region. The peak

Scheme 1. Fragmentation of MoO₂(AA)₂.

may be attributed to an ion produced due to the loss of CO, a ketene unit and at the same time an unit NHC_6H_5 . The fragment then underwent several fragmentations (Scheme 1) to generate other very intense peaks. So it was felt necessary to determine the molecular weight. The molecular weight was determined both by osmometry and freezing point depression methods which revealed the mononuclear nature of the complex.

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